

Manure Management Tools

Efficiency improvement of organic fertilizer application

Activities

- Use of conductivity meters to know in situ the nutrient content of soils and slurry.
- Application of different fertilizers at different time of crop growth with different application systems to compare crop quality
 - 6 cooperatives
 - Liquid and solid fraction of slurry and manure
 - Compost
 - Mineral fertilizers
 - Before sowing and during first growth of crops
 - Use of hoses or band spreaders
 - Different doses of organic fertilizers
- Perform of 4 training sessions to give quality and specialized advice to farmers depending on their cultural practices and soil characteristics.

Further details

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Objectives

The wide objective of the project was to develop innovative tools for manure management optimization and crop fertilization, from an economic and environmental sustainability point of view, in order to give the best advice to farmers.

Specifics objectives of application activity were:

- Improve efficiency of fertilizer application
- Reduce air, water and soil pollution from nitrogen from livestock manure
- Reduce GHG and ammonia emissions during the fertilizer application

Trailing shoes, band spreading and nutrient content measurement

Results

Different application timing with different kind of organic fertilizers and application systems gives different yield, growth and quality. The outcomes of different farms allowed the researchers to give specialized advice and training to the farmers.

The general conclusions of all tests are:

- Use of hoses is the best application system due to its uniformity, efficiency and facilities.
- Use of conductimeters is needed to know the correct amount of fertilizer to apply.
- Application of manure liquid fraction during first growth allows the absorption at the right moment.
- Two applications (70kg N/ha + 100kg N/ha) shows higher productivity than one application (170kg N/ha) with the same amount of nitrogen.
- Higher doses of nitrogen doesn't mean higher crop yield.
- It is necessary to plan application of manure and perform the best management during crops growth.

Context

Livestock manure has always been considered as a great resource for agriculture due they provide nutrients, keeping soil structure, improving its capacity to retain water and avoiding erosion.

During years, livestock farms has become more intensive, causing an increase of manure generation and its management problems.

Development of manure management tools to improve efficiency in manure application

Location in the Nutri-Know value chain

Manure goes from a resource to waste, which uncontrolled application to lands means a high risk of soil, air and water pollution.

Until 2014 manure was treated in heating plants, drying it using biogas, but then government approved the new legislation "Real Decret 413/2014" about use of renewable energy. This new legislation made impossible for these heating plants to keep working, so it becomes essential to find new strategies and solution for the manure management. It is mandatory to have a good manure management to optimize crops productivity, maximize productions and minimize environmental impacts. In addition, this manure management, complemented with good fertilizing practices and crop management, allows quality improvement in crops, having more economic profitability for farmers.

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